

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES TO LOGISTICS IN UZBEKISTAN'S TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This article explores the transformative impact of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) on Uzbekistan's logistics industry within the context of the tourism sector. The increasing need for information support and practical information management in tourism, driven by technological advancements, is highlighted. The study delves into how GIS systems are reshaping supply chains, optimizing routes, and redefining logistics operations in Uzbekistan. Through expert insights and real-world case studies, the potential of GIS in driving efficiency, innovation, and growth in the logistics landscape is showcased. The article envisions a future where information technology seamlessly integrates with logistics, paving the way for unparalleled industry optimization through geospatial intelligence.

Keywords: information technologies (IT), Geographic Information Systems (GIS), GIS systems, logistics, tourism, landscape, tourism logistics, travel, website, routing, tourists, tourism industry.

Tourism is pivotal in shaping a nation's economy and cultural identity. As Uzbekistan endeavors to position itself as a sought-after tourist destination, leveraging information technologies (IT) and integrating Geographic Information Systems (GIS) becomes paramount. In a world profoundly shaped by technology, industries are continually evolving to embrace innovation and optimization. Among these, the tourism sector is a vibrant arena where information technologies are pivotal in reshaping operations, enhancing customer experiences, and fostering sustainable growth. With Uzbekistan's charming landscapes and cultural treasures, integrating information technologies into its tourism logistics is not just a choice but a transformative necessity.

The tourism industry in Uzbekistan has witnessed remarkable growth over the past decade, emerging as a significant contributor to the country's economy and cultural identity. Nestled in the heart of Central Asia, Uzbekistan boasts a rich history, diverse cultural heritage, and a captivating blend of ancient traditions and modern aspirations. As the nation's tourism sector expands, there is an increasing need to address the logistical challenges of managing the influx of visitors and ensuring seamless travel experiences. Uzbekistan's tourism industry has experienced a transformative journey, transitioning from a relatively closed economy to an emerging global destination. The dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991 marked a pivotal moment for the country's tourism landscape, as it gained independence and began promoting its historical and cultural treasures to the world. Establishing diplomatic relations with various countries and implementing visa facilitation measures have further catalyzed inbound tourism growth.

The exploration of integrating information technologies and logistics within Uzbekistan's tourism industry holds paramount importance in the contemporary landscape of global tourism. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected and digitally driven, understanding how these advancements influence and transform the travel sector is imperative. This study's

significance lies in its potential to guide Uzbekistan’s tourism industry toward leveraging technology for enhanced operations, enriching visitor experiences, and positioning the nation competitively on the international stage. By delving into the literature surrounding this theme, we can uncover insights that bridge the gap between theory and practice, paving the way for sustainable growth, innovation, and cultural preservation within technology-driven tourism.

Information technologies (IT) have become integral to the modernization of logistics processes in the tourism industry worldwide. These technologies are crucial in improving efficiency, customer experience, and decision-making within the sector. In the case of Uzbekistan’s tourism industry, integrating I.T. in logistics presents numerous opportunities for growth, sustainability, and enhanced competitiveness.

Information technologies, including databases, inventory management systems, and real-time tracking tools, significantly enhance the efficiency of logistics operations. They enable businesses to manage resources, monitor inventory levels, and coordinate transportation seamlessly. According to a study by Moldabekova, IT systems have demonstrated their ability to improve logistics efficiency by reducing lead times and minimizing errors, thereby contributing to cost savings.

Figure 1. The main direction of the use of information technology in tourism. Source: compiled by Iyer et al., 2015., Abdullah et al., 2020, Moldabekova et al., 2021

S.F. Wamba et al. observed that information technologies provide greater visibility into the supply chain, allowing businesses to track the movement of goods, identify potential bottlenecks, and make real-time adjustments. This visibility is crucial in a complex industry like tourism, where factors such as seasonality, changing customer preferences, and unpredictable external events can impact logistics. According to a report by Sigala, supply chain visibility achieved through I.T. systems can help tourism companies respond effectively to disruptions and ensure consistent customer service.

In the highly competitive tourism sector, meeting customer expectations is crucial. Information technologies enable personalized services and experiences, contributing to higher customer satisfaction. Online booking platforms, mobile apps, and CRM systems facilitate seamless interactions between tourists and service providers.

The use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in the tourism industry refers to the application of advanced spatial data management and analysis tools to enhance decision-

making, resource allocation, and operational efficiency in various aspects of tourism. GIS technology enables users to visualize, interpret, and understand the relationships between different elements within a geographical context by integrating geographic and attribute data types. By leveraging GIS, tourism stakeholders can improve destination planning, marketing strategies, customer experiences, event management, and cultural heritage conservation. GIS solutions offer benefits such as route optimization, resource allocation, personalized services, and data-driven decision-making, ultimately enhancing the overall efficiency and satisfaction within the tourism sector.

This collaboration between technology and tourism in Uzbekistan shows a promising future for the industry. Travelers are increasingly supportive of integrating technology into their journeys, signaling a shift in expectations and a readiness for digital advancements in the tourism sector.

The growth in tourism in Uzbekistan, with a significant increase in the number of trips made from 2021 to 2022, highlights the country's appeal as a tourist destination. Despite existing tourist information resources, there is a need for a unified automated system that offers personalized services and payment options for tourists. The creation of such a system aligns with the government's efforts to develop the tourism industry, attract more tourists, and position Uzbekistan as a prominent tourist hub.

Among the various internet platforms for tourists in Uzbekistan, "UzbekistanTravel" stands out as a leading organization that promotes the country's beauty and historical sites using GIS technology. The platform provides travel resources, such as magazines, maps, and guides, as well as multimedia content like videos and photos, to showcase the country's attractions to a global audience.

In conclusion, the integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) with a robust tourism information platform in Uzbekistan marks a significant opportunity for transforming the tourism landscape in the country. By combining technology with traveler needs and aspirations, such a platform has the potential to revolutionize the way tourists engage with and experience Uzbekistan's diverse attractions. The emphasis on creating a user-centric design, implementing advanced GIS routing systems, offering personalized tour options, and ensuring data security and privacy underscores the importance of enhancing traveler experiences.

Furthermore, the recommendations outlined for crafting a comprehensive and user-centric platform highlight the essential elements needed to create a seamless and enriching experience for tourists. By fostering local partnerships, providing multilingual support, offering integrated booking systems, and continuously enhancing the platform, Uzbekistan can position itself as a leading destination for travelers seeking innovative and personalized tourism experiences.

References:

1. Abo-Zahhad, M., Ahmed, S. M., & Mourad, M. (2013). "Services and applications based on mobile user's location detection and prediction". *International Journal of Communications, Network and System Sciences*, 6(4), (pp. 167–175) Google scholar
2. Alnusairat, S., Elnaklah, R., Yajid MSA., Johar, MGM., Khatibi, A. (2021). "Information system, geography, information management system and tourism planning: a geographical

perspective from malaysia”. Palarch’s Journal of Vertebrate Palaeontology, 18(2) Google scolar

3. Bahaire, T. & Elliott-White, M. (1999). “The Application of Geographical Information Systems (GIS) in Sustainable Tourism Planning: A Review”. Journal of Sustainable Tourism, 7(2), (pp. 159-174) Google scolar

4. Braun, V., & Clarke, V., (2006). “Using thematic analysis in psychology”. Qualitative Research in Psychology, 3(2), (pp. 77-101) Google scolar

5. Buhalis, D., Law, R. (2008). “Progress in information technology and tourism management: 20 years on and 10 years after the Internet – The state of eTourism research”. Tourism Management, 29(4), (pp. 609-623) Google scolar

6. Cata, T., Patel, P. S., & Sakaguchi, T., (2013). “Q.R. code: A new opportunity for effective mobile marketing”. Journal of Mobile Technologies, Knowledge and Society, (pp. 1-7) Google scolar.

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